

Turning Research into Resolution: Wooptix's Vision for the Future of Chip Metrology

Best practice category

Materials, chemicals
and equipment

Stakeholder group

SMEs and start-ups

Value chain position

Equipment; R&D

General Information

Wooptix is a Spanish SME at the forefront of semiconductor metrology innovation through the wavefront phase imaging (WFPI) technique derived from adaptive optics research in astronomy. Born from a doctoral research project and based in Tenerife, Wooptix represents a successful case of an academic spin-off evolved into innovative industrial reality. The company develops high resolution and speed metrology optical solutions, for the analysis of wafer geometry and topography, both blank and pattern. Its flagship product, Phemet®, has already been installed with customers around the world, while the launch of a fully automated tool is scheduled for 2025: Alpha-FabTool.

Wooptix is recognised for its best practices in developing manufacturing equipment, collaborating R&D with academia, and creating an interdisciplinary innovation ecosystem, with applications also in areas such as microscopy and ophthalmology.

Activities and best practices

- Wooptix developed Phemet®, a laboratory instrument for metrology capable of inspecting the shape of wafers, both blank and pattern. The next launch of Alpha-FabTool, scheduled for 2025, will introduce a level of complete automation, responding to the growing precision needs of the most advanced technology nodes.
- Wooptix actively collaborates with research institutions such as the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC), exploiting a rich academic ecosystem. With over 150 scientific publications and more than 20 active R & D projects, the company represents a model of integration between scientific excellence and industrial application. In addition, the company's proximity to leading astrophysical observatories fosters access to highly specialised talent and supports the development of an open innovation ecosystem in the optics and photons sectors.

- Woptix is actively embedded in national and European public funding programmes aimed at supporting innovation in technology-intensive SMEs. Key projects funded include "Wide Angle & Resolution Metrology", 85% co-funded by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) under the Canary Islands Operational Programme 2014-2020, contributing to the objectives of Priority Axis 1: "Promoting research, technological development and innovation".
- The company is also the recipient of EATIC grants under the Canary Islands Intelligent Specialisation Strategy (RIS3), for projects in priority areas such as the high-resolution ocular analysis system and the development of a new hybrid automultiscopic 3D display. At national level, Woptix has obtained a prestigious Torres Quevedo grant, which has made it possible to strengthen its R & D team with highly qualified researchers, accelerating technological development in the field of wavefront metrology.

Challenges addressed with this practice

Woptix responds to the needs of high precision and automation in semiconductor metrology, fundamental for supporting the most advanced technological nodes. Its integration of academic research and industrial development addresses the challenge of bridging the gap between scientific innovation and practical applications in the field. In addition, the ability to attract and enhance specialised talent contributes to strengthening the European ecosystem of research-intensive technology SMEs.